

Apêndice A: Estratégias de busca e número de publicações identificadas por base de dados.

Base de dados	Estratégia de busca	Resultado
Pubmed	Search: ("Wolbachia"[Mesh] OR Wolbachia OR wMel) AND ("Aedes"[Mesh] OR "Aedes aegypti" OR "Zika Virus"[Mesh] OR ZikV OR "Zika virus" OR "Zika Virus Infection"[Mesh] OR "Dengue"[Mesh] OR Dengue OR "Dengue infection" OR "Dengue Virus"[Mesh] OR "Chikungunya virus"[Mesh] OR "Chikungunya Fever"[Mesh] OR Chikungunya OR "Arboviruses"[Mesh] OR "Arbovirus vector" OR "Arbovirus Infections"[Mesh] OR "Arbovirus Infection" OR Arboviruses)	707
CENTRAL	#1 MeSH descriptor: [Wolbachia] explode all trees #2 (Wolbachia OR wMel):ti,ab,kw #3 MeSH descriptor: [Aedes] explode all trees #4 MeSH descriptor: [Zika Virus] explode all trees #5 MeSH descriptor: [Zika Virus Infection] explode all trees #6 MeSH descriptor: [Dengue] explode all trees #7 MeSH descriptor: [Dengue Virus] explode all trees #8 MeSH descriptor: [Chikungunya virus] explode all trees #9 MeSH descriptor: [Chikungunya Fever] explode all trees #10 MeSH descriptor: [Arboviruses] explode all trees #11 MeSH descriptor: [Arbovirus Infections] explode all trees #12 (Aedes OR "Aedes aegypti" OR "Zika Virus" OR ZikV OR "Zika Virus Infection" OR Dengue OR "Dengue infection" OR "Dengue Virus" OR "Chikungunya virus" OR "Chikungunya Fever" OR Chikungunya OR Arboviruses OR "Arbovirus vector" OR "Arbovirus Infection*"):ti,ab,kw #13 #1 OR #2 #14 {OR #3-#12} #15 #13 AND #14	15
BVS	mh:("Wolbachia") OR (wolbachia OR wmel) AND mh:("Aedes" OR "Zika Virus" OR "Zika Virus Infection" OR "Dengue" OR "Dengue Virus" OR "Chikungunya virus" OR "Chikungunya Fever" OR "Arboviruses" OR "Arbovirus Infections") OR (aedes OR "Aedes aegypti" OR "Zika Virus" OR zikv OR "Zika Virus Infection" OR dengue OR "Dengue infection" OR "Dengue Virus" OR "Chikungunya virus" OR "Chikungunya Fever" OR chikungunya OR arboviruses OR "Arbovirus vector" OR "Arbovirus Infection" OR "Arbovirus Infections") AND (db:("LILACS" OR "SES-SP" OR "coleccionaSUS" OR "LIS" OR "PAHOIRIS" OR "campusvirtualsp_brasil" OR "BDENF" OR "IBECS" OR "VETINDEX"))	68
EMBASE	#13 #1 AND #12 #12 #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 #11 (aedes:ab,ti OR 'aedes aegypti':ab,ti OR 'zika virus':ab,ti OR zikv:ab,ti OR 'zika virus infection':ab,ti OR dengue:ab,ti OR 'dengue infection':ab,ti OR 'dengue virus':ab,ti OR 'chikungunya virus':ab,ti OR 'chikungunya fever':ab,ti OR chikungunya:ab,ti OR arboviruses:ab,ti OR 'arbovirus vector':ab,ti OR 'arbovirus infection':ab,ti) AND [embase]/lim #10 'arbovirus infection'/exp AND [embase]/lim #9 'arbovirus'/exp AND [embase]/lim #8 'chikungunya'/exp AND [embase]/lim #7 'chikungunya virus'/exp AND [embase]/lim #6 'dengue virus'/exp AND [embase]/lim #5 'dengue'/exp AND [embase]/lim #4 'zika fever'/exp AND [embase]/lim #3 'zika virus'/exp AND [embase]/lim #2 'aedes'/exp AND [embase]/lim #1 ('wolbachia'/exp OR 'wolbachia' OR 'wmel') AND [embase]/lim	663
ARCA Fiocruz	wolbachia AND (custo OR resist*)	253
TOTAL		1706
TOTAL SEM DUPLICADAS		1273

Data de acesso: 08/02/2022; duplicadas excluídas: 433; outras fontes = 2